

Performance Analysis and Comparative Study of Equity Linked Savings Schemes (ELSS) in India

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Abstract

This research paper aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of Equity Linked Savings Schemes (ELSS) in India, focusing on their performance, tax benefits, and suitability for various investor profiles. The study examines the historical performance of select ELSS funds over the past five years, analyzing annual returns and average growth rates. Additionally, it compares ELSS with other tax-saving instruments, such as Public Provident Fund (PPF), National Savings Certificate (NSC), 5-Year Tax-Saving Fixed Deposits, and National Pension System (NPS), in terms of lock-in period, risk level, expected returns, and tax deductions under Section 80C. The research also offers insights into the investing class for ELSS and key factors to consider while selecting ELSS funds. By providing a thorough analysis and comparison, this paper aims to guide investors in making informed decisions to achieve their financial objectives while optimizing tax benefits.

Introduction

Diverse equities funds comprise the equities Linked Savings Scheme. The main asset class of these funds is listed company stock. The stocks are selected from a variety of industries and market capitalizations, including large, mid, and small caps. The long-term goal of these funds is to maximize capital appreciation. After completing extensive market research, the fund manager selects equities in order to provide the best risk-adjusted portfolio returns.

Section 80C of the Income Tax Act of 1961 allows for tax benefits on investments made in an ELSS fund. The IT Act allows for a tax deduction of up to Rs. 1.5 lakh, but there is no upper limit to the amount that can be invested. One can reduce their annual tax liability by up to ₹46,800 by putting their money into an ELSS.

Equity Linked Savings Schemes (ELSS) represent a significant investment avenue in India, blending the potential for high returns with tax-saving benefits under Section 80C of the Income Tax Act, 1961. These mutual funds invest predominantly in stocks of listed companies, with a diverse portfolio spanning across market capitalization and sectors. Aimed at maximizing capital

Received: 2 March 2024

Revised: 12 March 2024

Final Accepted 27 March 2024

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10887273>

appreciation over the long term, ELSS funds are managed by expert fund managers who conduct rigorous market research to construct portfolios that deliver optimal risk-adjusted returns. Investors can avail tax deductions of up to Rs. 1.5 lakh annually by investing in ELSS, resulting in substantial tax savings of up to ₹46,800 per year. With a minimum lock-in period of three years, ELSS offers market-linked returns dependent on the performance of the underlying equities, making it an attractive option for individuals seeking higher returns on their investment portfolios, particularly salaried individuals and first-time investors. Compared to alternative tax-saving instruments like ULIPs and the National Pension System (NPS), ELSS stands out with its shorter lock-in period and potential for higher returns. Additionally, considerations such as fund returns, fund house reputation, expense ratio, financial parameters, and fund manager expertise play crucial roles in ELSS fund selection. The choice between SIPs and lumpsum investments further adds flexibility to investors' strategies, with SIPs often favored for their cost averaging benefits. Overall, ELSS emerges as a versatile and rewarding investment avenue, offering a blend of tax benefits and wealth creation potential for investors across different risk profiles and investment horizons.

Review of Literature

Arul Prasad.P. and Vijayakumar.L. (2017) examined how several demographic factors affected investors' perceptions of mutual funds. In addition, it highlighted the advantages that investors receive from mutual funds. Respondents with varying demographic features were polled for this study. According to the report, most investors are not interested in investing in mutual funds.

In their 2016 study, B. Kishori and N. Bhagyasree examined the effectiveness of transition economy open-ended, growth-oriented equity programs. According to the analysis, the returns on 14 of the 30 mutual fund schemes had surpassed the benchmark. The outcomes also demonstrated that a lack of diversification was a factor in some of the schemes' poor performance. All of the schemes in the analysis had positive Sharpe ratios, indicating that the funds were yielding returns higher than the risk-free rate.

Aashish Jain (2017) in his study made an attempt to evaluate the performance tax savings mutual funds through statistical tools like return, standard deviation, Coefficient of variation, Sharpe ratio, Treynor ratio and Jensen alpha. The main purpose of the study was to compare five ELSS scheme of public sector and private sector. Investing in mutual funds is very popular among small investors to seek tax incentives. Taxefficient mutual fund plans or equity-linked savings schemes provide investors with tax relief. Therefore, the research was conducted to meet the investors' goals. It would be concluded from the study that DSPBR Tax saver fund (G) outperformed amongst selected schemes.

Khalid Ashraf Chisti & Amir Rahman (2018) evaluated the performance of top 10 tax saving mutual fund schemes operating in India. Performance was evaluated according to annual returns

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Final Accepted 27 March 2024

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and compared to the NIFTY50 benchmark index using various statistical tools like average return, beta, Sharpe ratio, Treynor ratio and Jensen alpha. The study concluded that all ELSS funds outperform the market index in terms of average return and were risky except for certain schemes; with the exception of Aditya Birla Sunlife Tax Relief, all funds performed more steadily than the benchmark. In addition, axis fund was the most trustworthy scheme in market; likewise, all the funds have positive relationship with the market.

Richa Pathak (2018) investigated performance of ELSS Growth funds using various tools like Beta, Sharpe ratio, Jensen ratio etc. Also proposed appropriate ELSS mutual fund so that the investors can achieve their investment goals. The research was undertaken for the period of 5 years and 10 ELSS growth funds was analysed. Research shows that the ELSS-Growth Fund is above the benchmark index and was well.

Objectives:

1. To analyze the historical performance of select ELSS funds over the past five years.
2. To evaluate the average growth rates of ELSS funds to understand their consistency in delivering returns.
3. To compare ELSS with other tax-saving instruments in terms of lock-in period, risk level, expected returns, and tax benefits.
4. To provide insights into the suitability of ELSS for different investor profiles, such as salaried individuals and first-time investors.
5. To highlight key factors to consider while selecting ELSS funds, including fund returns, fund house history, expense ratio, financial parameters, and fund manager expertise.
6. To offer recommendations for investors based on the findings of the study and their individual investment goals and risk appetite.

Research Methodology

- The research primarily rely on publicly available data sourced from reputable financial platforms such as S&P BSE Sensex and Moneycontrol.com.
- Historical performance data of select Equity Linked Savings Scheme (ELSS) funds will be collected for the past five years, including annual returns and average growth rates.
- Information on other tax-saving instruments like Public Provident Fund (PPF), National Savings Certificate (NSC), 5-Year Tax-Saving Fixed Deposits, and National Pension System (NPS) will also be gathered to facilitate comparative analysis.
- The collected data is analyzed to assess the performance consistency of ELSS funds over the study period.

Received: 2 March 2024

Revised: 12 March 2024

Final Accepted 27 March 2024

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10887273>

Data Analysis and results

One can increase tax savings returns by using alternative tax-saving products available on the market. These assets have fixed returns, which might not be able to outpace the impact of inflation. This isn't the case with ELSS, though, since it makes investments in stocks that have a high chance of producing positive returns that outpace inflation. It is also the only tax-saving plan with a three-year lock-in term that is the shortest. Below given is the comparison:

Table 1: comparison between ELSS and other tax-saving instruments:

ELSS Vs. Other Tax Saving Schemes					
Investments	ELSS	Public Provident Fund (PPF)	National Savings Certificate (NSC)	5 Year Tax-Saving Fixed Deposits	National Pension System (NPS)
Type of Investment	Mutual Fund (Equity)	Government Scheme	Government Scheme	Bank Fixed Deposit	Pension Scheme
Lock-in Period	3 years	15 years	5 years	5 years	60 years age
Risk Level	High	Low	Low	Low	Moderate to High
Expected Returns	Market-linked	7.1% (Keeps changing)	7.7% (Keeps changing)	Around 6% to 7%	Market-linked
Tax Deduction Limit (Section 80C)	Up to ₹1.5 lakh	Up to ₹1.5 lakh	Up to ₹1.5 lakh	Up to ₹1.5 lakh	Up to ₹1.5 lakh

Source: <https://www.etmoney.com/learn/mutual-funds/elss-mutual-funds/>

Equity Linked Savings Scheme (ELSS) stands out among various tax-saving options due to its investment nature primarily focused on equity markets, making it a type of mutual fund. Unlike other schemes like the Public Provident Fund (PPF) or National Savings Certificate (NSC), ELSS offers a shorter lock-in period of 3 years, providing investors with relatively quicker liquidity. However, this shorter term comes with higher risk, as ELSS investments are subject to market fluctuations. While the returns from ELSS are market-linked and thus can vary significantly, they have the potential to surpass the fixed returns offered by PPF, NSC, or tax-saving fixed deposits. These traditional schemes, characterized by low risk and longer lock-in periods, offer stable but comparatively lower returns. Moreover, investments in the National Pension System (NPS), which span until retirement age, offer moderate to high risk and returns, being market-linked like ELSS. Importantly, all these investments fall under the Section 80C tax

deduction limit of up to ₹1.5 lakh, providing taxpayers with avenues to save on taxes while meeting their long-term financial goals. Ultimately, the choice between ELSS and other tax-saving schemes depends on an individual's risk appetite, investment horizon, and financial objectives.

Equity-linked savings schemes (ELSS), the performance of various funds over the past five years

Chart 1: Performance analysis

In the realm of equity-linked savings schemes (ELSS), the performance of various funds fluctuated over the past five years, reflecting the volatility inherent in equity markets. Among the mentioned funds, the SBI Long Term Equity Fund - Regular Plan - Growth exhibited impressive growth rates in 2021 and 2023, with returns soaring to 29% and 39%, respectively. Similarly, the ITI ELSS Tax Saver Fund and Motilal Oswal ELSS Tax Saver Fund experienced substantial growth in 2023, registering returns of 38%. However, the performance of these funds varied across different years, with fluctuations evident in their annual returns. For instance, while the Bank of India ELSS Tax Saver - Direct Plan - Growth achieved significant growth in 2020 and 2021, with returns of 32% and 41% respectively, its performance in other years was more modest. On the other hand, the Baroda BNP Paribas ELSS Tax Saver Fund witnessed mixed results, with negative returns in 2022 but positive growth in other years. Overall, investors in ELSS funds experienced a mix of highs and lows, emphasizing the importance of understanding market dynamics and conducting thorough research before making investment decisions.

The average growth rate for the last five years

Chart 2: Comparative Analysis

The average growth rate for the last five years provides a comprehensive view of the performance consistency of each ELSS fund. In this context, the SBI Long Term Equity Fund - Regular Plan - Growth maintained a steady average growth rate of 19.54%, reflecting its ability to deliver consistent returns over the period. Similarly, the ITI ELSS Tax Saver Fund - Direct Plan - Growth and the Motilal Oswal ELSS Tax Saver Fund - Direct Plan - Growth showcased commendable average growth rates of 16.41% and 19.31% respectively, indicating relatively stable performance over the five-year period.

On the other hand, the Bank of India ELSS Tax Saver - Direct Plan - Growth exhibited a higher average growth rate of 24.97%, suggesting a more aggressive growth trajectory compared to its peers. Despite potential fluctuations in performance from year to year, this fund displayed strong overall growth over the five-year span. Meanwhile, the Baroda BNP Paribas ELSS Tax Saver Fund - Direct Plan - Growth maintained a respectable average growth rate of 18.09%, demonstrating consistent growth albeit at a slightly lower pace compared to some of the other funds.

Overall, analyzing the average growth rates for the last five years provides investors with valuable insights into the historical performance stability of each ELSS fund, helping them make informed decisions based on their risk tolerance and investment objectives.

Conclusion

Equity Linked Savings Schemes (ELSS) in India have emerged as popular tax-saving investment options offering the dual benefits of potential high returns and tax deductions under Section 80C. Through the analysis of historical performance and comparison with other tax-saving instruments, this study demonstrates the advantages of ELSS, including shorter lock-in periods, market-linked returns, and diversified equity exposure. Furthermore, the research highlights the suitability of ELSS for different investor profiles, such as salaried individuals seeking higher returns and first-time investors looking to gain exposure to equity markets. By considering key factors like fund returns, fund house history, expense ratio, and fund manager expertise, investors can make well-informed decisions to maximize their investment returns while minimizing tax liabilities. Overall, ELSS remains a compelling investment avenue for long-term wealth creation and tax planning strategies in India.

Mutual funds that save taxes are called Equity Linked Savings Schemes, or ELSS in India. They combine Section 80C tax deductions with the advantages of equity investing. Long-term investors favor ELSS because of its 3-year lock-in period, which allows for tax savings and the possibility of large gains.

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